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San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

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ADDRESSING GRADE ONE NON- DECODER RATE THROUGH PROJECT READ: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION PROGRAM

LIZA T. CASUYON, MAEd

Teacher III

*Jesus SM Cabarrus Elementary School
Division of Antipolo City -Region IVA*

Purpose

This action research aims to address the non-decoder rate of grade one pupils through the Continuous Improvement Plan (Project READ) and develop an intervention Program which will support the project for the school year 2018-2019.

Design

The researcher is basically quantitative in nature as it utilized quasi-experimental method to determine the proper procedure on the CI Project (READ). This method of research requires pre-assessment and post assessment the results of which are compared to measure the effectiveness of the intervention used by the researcher.

Findings

After a thorough analysis of data, the researchers found out that after the implementation of the CI Project (READ) there is a decreased of Grade non-decoder for SY 2018-2019. It is indicated that the school had made an effective implementation plan in addressing the non-decoder of grade one pupils.

Research Implications/Limitation

This study was delimited to grade one pupil for school year 2018-2019. This study will serve as basis for Intervention Program in line with the improvement on schools' non-decoder as reflected in the Continuous Improvement steps.

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Originality

The research was crafted in line with the results of completed Continuous Improvement (CI) Project READ-Read to Excel on Advancing Development

Keywords: Project READ, Continuous Improvement, Non-decoder Rate, Intervention Program

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